

Implicature of Jokes in Broadcast Messages

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Abstract : The study of implicature which is one of the discussions of pragmatics is an interesting and challenging topic to discuss. Implicature is a meaning which is implied in an utterance which is not the same as its literal meaning. The rapid development of information technology results in social networks as media to broadcast messages. The broadcast messages may be in the form of jokes which contain implicature. The research applies the pragmatic equivalent method to analyze the topics of jokes based on the implicatures contained in them. Furthermore, the method is also applied to reveal the purpose of creating implicature in jokes. The findings include the kinds of implicature found in jokes which are classified into conventional implicature and conversational implicature. Then, in detailed analysis, implicature in jokes is divided into implicature related to gender, culture, and social phenomena. Furthermore, implicature in jokes may not only be used to give entertainment but also to soften criticisms or satire so that it does not sound rude and harsh.

Keywords : implicature, broadcast messages, conventional implicature, conversational implicature

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